

Harmonizing Ethics in Living Labs

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Background and aims

This research is focused on the harmonization of ethics in Living Labs (LLs). Living Lab (LL) is known as an approach to managing open innovation processes in which quadruple helix actors of innovation (i.e., public, private research institutions, and users) are involved to co-create innovation in a real-life setting (Leminen & Westerlund, 2012; Schuurman, 2015). Today, it is vital to ensure that innovation development in LLs is in line with ethical principles and societal values, the so-called Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) (Owen et al., 2012). By digging deeper into the ethical dimensions of LLs, this research aims to harmonize ethics in LLs. Through a short literature review and workshop, the research navigates the ethical challenges of LL activities, striving for a harmonious integration of ethical considerations in LLs.

Methods

To accomplish the research objective, a literature search was conducted according to Webster and Watson's guidelines (2002), followed by a workshop in OLLD23 conference, to discuss the findings. The literature review aimed to categorize existing research on LL ethics and RRI. The workshop employed a Reverse Brainstorming method (Woods & Davies, 1973) to creatively extract potential issues related to LL activities' ethics and responsibility.

Results

LL practices, by nature, need to align with RRI principles, especially when dealing with the ethical challenges posed by advanced technologies. The first ethical consideration in LL activities is whether user engagement is totally voluntary or not. As Ley et al. (2015) argue, in many cases, users feel obliged to participate in LL activities despite the fact that their participation is defined as "voluntary." When it comes to group activities, users might have to join the group activities due to group pressure (Löfman, Pelkonen, and Pietilä, 2004). This pressure to participate can make it difficult for the voluntary contributors to withdraw from the activity or refuse to participate (Magnusson and Hanson 2003). Overlooking the users' interest in LL activities is also an important ethical consideration. As mentioned by Mulder and Stappers (2009), "Living Labs seem to operate with the implicit assumption that users are cheap or unpaid contributors, motivated by the anticipation that their participation will solve their problems or lead to 'better' designs" (p. 2).

Unwitting participation in LL activities occurs when users are unable to opt out, as e.g., seen in monitoring infrastructures in public spaces like airports. This lack of choice raises ethical concerns, emphasizing the importance of allowing users the freedom to withdraw

from such activities, even in public settings (Mensink et al., 2010). Moreover, in LL research involving families, securing informed consent is challenging, particularly with children at home (Krogstie et al., 2013). Emphasizing transparency about engagement's purpose, benefits, and risks is also an important aspect (Mensink et al., 2010).

The increasing use of technology in LLs in various domains also raises ethical considerations, such as bias, accountability, transparency, dehumanization of actions, digital divide, and privacy issues (Kim et al., 2021; Nadoleanu et al., 2022; Saurabh et al., 2021). These challenges are particularly important in the context of LL actions (Harbers & Overdiek, 2022), which are real-world settings for research and innovation activities.

During the workshop, the importance of transparency became evident, involving clear communication of goals, processes, and outcomes to diverse stakeholders. Stakeholder engagement prioritized the voice and influence of all actors, addressing the challenge of ensuring inclusivity in the digital transition era. The commitment to aligning technology-driven innovations with ethical principles, emphasizing issues such as user privacy, bias, and accountability, was also highlighted. Regarding sustainability in LLs, the focus was on responsible resource use, reducing environmental impact, and finding a balance between rapid innovation and long-term sustainability goals.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study, centred on harmonizing ethics in LLs, reveals the necessary need for ethical considerations as technology integrates further into daily life. Ethical dimensions explored in LLs, addressing user engagement, group dynamics, unwitting participation, and transparency challenges, highlight crucial aspects for ethical integration. The workshop underlined transparency, stakeholder engagement, ethical considerations, and sustainability as key in aligning technology-driven innovations with ethical principles within LLs, navigating complexities introduced by technological advancements. This research contributes valuable insights for fostering ethical practices in LLs, promoting responsible and inclusive technological integration.

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